

LEVEL OF EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT AT ABC TECHNOLOGY SOLUTIONS COMPANY: BASIS FOR EMPLOYEE RETENTION STRATEGIES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14226775>

ABSTRACT

The chosen technology solutions company is facing a dilemma about employees leaving the company; hence they are experiencing low retention rates. In 2023, their attrition rate was at 14.9% and most of the employees leaving the company are IT specialists and software engineers. This study determined the level of employee reaction to the existing retention strategies of the subject firm based on the three engagement factors which are achievement, camaraderie and equity. The research employed an opinion-based research method through a researcher-made questionnaire. The survey was conducted with 82 employee respondents. The percentage of employee reactions were measured and assessed, and they provided a strong insight into the areas that needed improvement. Under each engagement factor, the elements which received most of the negative employee reactions were the focus of strategy enhancement. For the 'achievement' factor, respondents answered that initiatives for training and learning opportunities (35%) must be improved. In terms of 'camaraderie' factor, open interaction with colleagues from different teams (12%) garnered the highest negative employee reactions. This implies that various activities must be organized to meet peers inside the workplace and there must be better communication between departments or teams as this is beneficial for both productivity and customer experience. In connection with 'equity', providing variable pay (38%) got mostly negative employee reactions. The employees who completed the survey indicated that performance bonuses or commissions should also be given to employees who were below managerial level. This approach will reinforce the sense of accomplishment for individual contributors or team members. The retention strategy enhancement recommendations included customized training opportunities for different levels of the workforce as well as training needs assessment to close skill gaps, provision of variable pay for all positions and communication programs to improve

connection and collaboration of departments or teams. Aside from that, a general recommendation for adapting a data-driven HR model was also provided. These proposed interventions aimed at helping to improve the employee retention strategies, which will result in higher engagement levels and better employee retention rates.

Keywords: *Employee Engagement, Employee Retention, Retention Strategies, Achievement, Camaraderie, Equity*

INTRODUCTION

Nature and Scope of the Problem Investigated

One of the industries experiencing high turnover rates is technology. As mentioned by Chen (2023) in her article entitled *The True Cost of Employee Turnover in Tech*, technology companies have the highest turnover rate compared to any industry at 13.20%. This is the highest turnover rate of any sector and emphasizes the important problem that tech companies are facing. A growing talent shortage have created a culture of fierce competition amongst tech employers. To address this issue, retention strategies of a selected technology solutions company were studied to find out which can be enhanced to also improve retention rates. The said organization is currently experiencing high attrition at 14.9% in 2023. The employees who were leaving the company were offered more compelling pay and benefits from competitors, especially because the knowledge and skills they possess are in demand nowadays. Most of them were software engineers and IT specialists. Other reasons cited by employees during exit interviews include limited career advancement, lack of recognition for their outputs and accomplishments as well as unhappiness with the management style of their superiors.

With the mentioned causes of resignations, this study explored employee engagement as it is viewed as a strong strategic tool that aids the retention of the best talent that will guarantee effective organizational performance. Moreover, looking into the areas of achievement, camaraderie, and equity will reveal ways on how the organization can decrease attrition rates by enhancing retention strategies to make employees want to stay in the organization longer. When organizations and leaders can retain their people, they benefit from preserving institutional knowledge, reducing recruitment, and training costs, diminishing disruption, and fostering a steadier and more driven workforce focused on accomplishing goals.

Review of Pertinent Literatures

The engagement model conceptualized by David Sirota explains the objectives of the organization which include retention, customer satisfaction, innovation, and financial performance. This would be achieved by building great connections among the employees, forming fair systems and policies, equal opportunity for career growth and improving leadership and management practices to produce higher levels of enthusiasm and engagement.

The first engagement factor is achievement. People want to be proud of the work that they do, and they want their accomplishments to be recognized. To help people feel this sense of achievement, an organization needs to do the following:

- Provide an enabling work environment by giving employees what they need to do the job well.
- Provide challenging work by allowing workers to do valuable work that utilizes their full abilities.
- Use feedback, recognition, and reward to inform employees how they are doing.
- Be an organization of purpose and principles as workers want to work for trustworthy companies that they can be proud of.

The second engagement factor is camaraderie. When people go to the workplace, they want to enjoy themselves. That makes social relationships essential. A culture that supports and encourages communication, openness, acceptance, and teamwork is substantial for maintaining enthusiasm. As such, partnership needs to be a key part of company culture (Murthy, 2021).

The last engagement factor is equity. People are motivated by fair treatment, and they want their company to give basic conditions that respect their physiological, economic, and psychological needs. It covered the following elements:

- Physiological safety which ensures the physical safety of workers.
- Economic security provides a reasonable level of job security. Layoffs are usually part of larger business decisions which may be due to mergers, acquisitions, or strategy changes. There is a need to share facts about the layoff, why the layoff is taking place. Also, there is a need to give assistance to laid-off workers and provide support for the remaining employees as they might feel overwhelmed and worried about the future as well
- Providing fair compensation.
- Psychological health creates an environment of respect (Edwards, 2024).

By creating an environment that attends to all three factors, companies can better ensure high satisfaction, motivation, productivity, and favorable business outcomes (Sirota et al., 2005).

Research Framework

The research paradigm below was utilized to accomplish the goal of this study.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework followed a sequential structure. It sought to determine and assess levels of employee reaction on the retention strategies for the three engagement factors, which are achievement, camaraderie, and equity. There were two data sources which were analyzed; these were the employee reactions and the existing retention strategies. In the first step, existing retention strategies were requested from the HR Department of the organization. Then, these strategies were compiled and listed according to the three engagement factors. Afterwards, all retention strategies for each engagement factor were included in the questionnaire for a more organized data analysis.

The next procedure was to administer the online questionnaire and gather the employee reactions on the current retention strategies. Afterwards, levels of employee reaction were assessed. The percentage for each engagement factor and elements under each factor were presented to determine which were scoring high (Levels 3 and 4 – Satisfaction and Enthusiasm) and those scoring low (Levels 1 and 2 – Indifference and Anger). Such information helped identify the good points to maintain as well as the areas where enhancement was needed for the current employee retention strategies being implemented.

Research Questions

This research focused on determining and assessing the engagement level of employees as the basis for enhancing employee retention strategies. To accomplish such intent, the following questions were raised:

1. What are the existing retention strategies for each engagement factor:
 - a. Achievement
 - b. Camaraderie
 - c. Equity
2. What is the level of employee reaction on existing retention strategies based on these engagement factors:
 - a. Achievement
 - b. Camaraderie
 - c. Equity
3. What strategies should be enhanced to improve employee retention based on the employees' reaction?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This quantitative study aimed to determine the level of employee reaction to existing retention strategies based on the engagement factors: achievement, camaraderie, and equity. After the level of employee reactions to the engagement factors had been identified, it was used as a basis to enhance the existing employee retention strategies of the organization. For this research, an online survey was utilized. The questionnaire contained a total of 27 statements to cover the three factors of achievement (12 statements), camaraderie (3 statements), and equity (12 statements). All respondents were asked to rate the statements using David Sirota's 4-point scale. Four (4) is the highest reaction which means enthusiasm and one (1) is the lowest reaction which signifies anger. Their responses were treated as an individual source of data. The researcher applied a cross-sectional study which focused on only one period.

Research Locale

The study was conducted at ABC Technology Solutions. It is a provider of human resources software and services for all organizational sizes. The said firm was selected to be the research locale as it belongs to the technology industry and was experiencing high employee turnover as most of their talents have knowledge and skills which are very in demand in the current labor market.

The total headcount was 133 employees who were directly hired but only those who were with the company for one year or more were considered part of the population. These employees had been remote workers even before the pandemic; hence the questionnaire was sent via Microsoft Forms.

Population and Sampling Design

Among the 133 employees of ABC Technology Solutions, 82 of them have been working in the company for at least a year. All these 82 employees participated in this research. The respondents were refined in that way to ensure that they already have good appreciation and ample experience of the employee retention strategies implemented by the company. Total enumeration was applied for this study.

Research Instruments

This study used a questionnaire to determine the level of employee reaction to the three engagement factors. Under each factor, there are several engagement elements to further specify the statements to be rated.

Table 1. Elements for each Engagement Factor (Dr. David Sirota, 2005)

Engagement Factors	Elements	No. of Statements
Achievement	Enabling Work Environment	3
	Providing Challenging Work	3
	Use of Feedback, Recognition and Reward	3
	Organization of Purpose and Principles	3
Comaraderie	Partnership Culture	3
Equity	Physiological Safety	3
	Economic Security	3
	Fair Compensation	3
	Psychological Health	3
Total		27

Under each element, open-ended questions were included in the online survey to ask for reasons regarding the respondents' answers. A space for inputs and suggestions was also present. The respondents rated each statement on the online survey using the 4-point scale. The levels of employee reactions have an equivalent score as displayed on the table below:

Table 2. The 4-Point Scale to Determine Employee Reaction (Sirota, 2005)

Level of Reaction	Reaction Score	Reaction Level
Enthusiasm	4	Positive Employee Reaction
Satisfaction	3	
Indifference	2	Negative Employee Reaction
Anger	1	

Data Gathering Procedure

To gather the needed data for this study, the following procedures were conducted. First, the researcher got the approval of the company for data gathering. Next, a list of existing retention strategies implemented in the workplace was requested from the HR Manager. Right after, the strategies were compiled and organized according to the three engagement factors. The results of this were sent back to the HR Manager to confirm if the retention strategies were listed under the correct engagement factors. Once confirmed, the organized retention strategies were included in the questionnaire to serve as the basis of the respondents in rating each statement. Then, the research instrument was administered to all respondents using Microsoft Forms. The link to the survey was sent via email. This approach was selected as all respondents were working from home. Based on the respondents' feelings and overall experience, they rated the existing retention strategies related to the engagement factors which are achievement, camaraderie, and equity.

Management and Treatment of Data

The data gathered from the survey were compiled and percentages of the employee reactions were analyzed as they indicated the overall enthusiasm of the respondents to

the current retention strategies. The scores implied whether the efforts exerted by the company were working well or not. The results of the analysis provided valuable inputs to enhance the current strategies and likewise improve the organization's retention rates.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Existing retention strategies of the organization

In terms of 'achievement', the company implements professional enhancement programs as well as recognition programs which are both valuable to the employees. The first one allows the employees to learn more about their job and their other roles in the organization while the second one recognizes their commitment, contribution and adherence to the company's core values. For 'camaraderie', aside from the groups and committees they currently have, the company also focuses on social and charity work which reinforces fellowship and solidarity among employees. These strategies allow employees to connect and collaborate with colleagues within and outside their teams as well as to do meaningful deeds for those who are in need. Lastly, there are also existing strategies for the 'equity' factor. Programs revolve around wellness, work-life balance and monetary incentive. Such programs permit employees to live a healthy lifestyle and pursue their interests or passion aside from their work.

Employee reactions on existing retention strategies based on the engagement factors

For the achievement factor, *Organization of Purpose and Principles* received a total of 93% of positive employee reactions. It demonstrates that the employees believed in the vision, purpose, and leadership of the organization and they were confident with the company's quality of products and services. According to Tenney (2020), When employees feel a shared sense of purpose with their co-workers and a strong commitment to the company's mission, vision, and values, this results in enhancement of engagement, morale, productivity, trust, and overall job satisfaction.

On the other hand, *Providing Challenging Work* under achievement gained most of the negative employee reactions at 19%. This means that respondents wanted improvements in terms of using their full capabilities, learning how they can further contribute to the company and having more training opportunities. Employees would want their skills and knowledge to continuously improve. Creating an environment that values growth and learning will enable staff members to flourish in their roles (Tenney, 2020).

In terms of camaraderie, the specific area of *Employees Demonstrating Empathy, Consideration, and Respect* received the highest positive employee reactions of 94%. Respondents mentioned that they felt they belonged and included in the organization despite working remotely. Indeed, a work environment infused with camaraderie is more likely to have higher levels of employee engagement. Workers who feel connected to their

colleagues and work as part of a supportive team tends to be motivated, passionate, and dedicated towards their job (Vance, 2023).

Meanwhile, *Openly Interacting with other Teams* under camaraderie factor garnered most of the negative employee reactions at 12%. In the survey form, some respondents commented that there should be more social connection programs conducted to further enhance communication and camaraderie. This showcases the natural inclination of people to have meaningful relations. When people go to the workplace, they want to enjoy themselves. That makes social relationships essential (Murthy, 2021). Moreover, it can be a powerful tool for organizations because friendly discussions can positively develop into innovative collaborations to help teams, and the company thrive (Shoobridge, 2020).

About the equity factor, the highest positive overall employee reaction percentage can be seen in *Physiological Safety* (96%). This engagement element focuses on work-life balance and physical safety. Comments on the survey form were focused on how the employees appreciated the remote work set-up as well as the flexibility in terms of working hours. It greatly contributed to their work-life balance making it manageable for them to spread work throughout the day while also doing chores at home and spending time with their families. Such a result validated the statement of Paulsen (2021). He mentioned that when the workforce is given work-life flexibility, they are less likely to feel burnt out. Moreover, many workers have realized they are no longer constrained by the hours of a traditional workweek, particularly when it means long commutes and being away from their families (Radley, 2022).

On the contrary, most of the negative employee reactions can be observed in *Fair Compensation* under equity factor. It gained an overall negative employee reaction percentage of 22%. This indicates that the respondents were clamoring for better compensation and incentives. It was noted by a lot of respondents that the yearly salary increase was insignificant, especially with the continuous price increase of commodities. They were suggesting for a salary review and realignment as they saw a lot of their colleagues resigning because of offers of better compensation and benefits from other companies. Such results aligned with the statement that pay, and other benefits are important as they serve as the main motivation why employees seek a new job. That is why the pay should be competitive with other firms to avoid workers from resigning. It is best to thoroughly assess the abilities required and duties to be performed for each position when constructing pay structures and it must be adjusted periodically to keep it competitive (Paulsen, 2021).

Strategies to be Enhanced to Improve Employee Retention

Based on the responses given by employees, the specific areas under each engagement factor must be the focus of strategy enhancement efforts. These areas received most of the negative employee reactions (see Table 3). With such results, the management team and the HR Department need to focus on these areas to convince employees to stay in the company longer.

Table 3. Specific areas of engagement to be enhanced to improve employee retention

Engagement Factor	Engagement Element	Specific Area	Percentage of Negative Employee Reaction
Achievement	Enabling Work Environment	Leaders delegate tasks effectively	14%
	Providing Challenging Work	Provided with training and learning opportunities	35%
	Using Feedback, Recognition and Reward	Provides tangible rewards	27%
	Organization of Purpose and Principles	Leaders' actions are consistent with their words	20%
Camaraderie	Partnership Culture	Can openly interact with colleagues from different teams	12%
Equity	Physiological Safety	Has work-life balance	12%
	Economic Security	Communicates openly and honestly about layoffs	15%
	Fair Compensation	Provided with variable pay	38%
	Psychological Health	Pays attention to the wants and needs of employees	28%

A. Achievement Factor

From the results mentioned in Table 3, these are the suggestions and recommendations to enhance employee engagement for the 'achievement' factor. These recommendations focus on improving specific areas of each engagement element which are enabling the work environment, providing challenging work, using feedback, recognition and rewards as well as organization of purpose and principles.

Table 4. Suggestions and recommendations to enhance specific areas of ‘achievement’ factor to improve employee retention

Specific Area	Enhancement Suggestions
Leaders delegate tasks effectively	<p>From respondents:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Have a clearly defined Standard Operation Procedures (SOP) for all functions. <p>Based on related studies:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Provide employees with enough autonomy as well as the resources they need to do their job well (Tenney, 2020). 2. Leaders must be approachable and must convey objectives with utmost clarity. 3. Consider members’ abilities before establishing policies or delegating responsibilities (Ganesh, 2022).
Provided with training and learning opportunities	<p>From respondents:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Offer development opportunities for Millennials and Gen Zs to prepare them for leadership roles in the future. 2. Clearly define the hierarchy, contact persons and knowledge-sharing points <p>Based on related studies:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Perform training needs assessment so that learning programs are customized to the needs of the employees (Paulsen, 2021). 2. Provide opportunities for learning specifically made for different levels of the workforce (Brown, 2022). 3. Trainings in technical, behavioral, mental, financial, and competency areas are strategic investments in people that promote a culture of adaptation and constant progress. Also, it makes the organization future ready (Gupta, 2024). 4. Consider Small Group Activities or Employee Committees as it gives workers the freedom to freely express themselves. Aside from having a platform to share their thoughts and concerns, it also allows them to assume leadership positions within the said committees which gives them exposure in handling team members (Sarma, 2023).
Provides tangible rewards	<p>From respondents:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Managers should be required to encourage their members to achieve professional growth. 2. Give rewards and recognition for notable contributions. <p>Based on related studies:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Outline a clear path to advancement and prioritize internal hires and promotions (Paulsen, 2021). 2. Employees need to know clear parameters on how they are monitored and how targets are measured and rewarded (Brown, 2022). 3. For Gen Z employees, incentives can be an important retention tool. They prefer frequent and authentic recognition like shopping points, gift cards, and travel incentives (Hatch, 2024).
Leaders’ actions are consistent with their words	<p>From respondents:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Clarifying the operating model and decision hierarchy. <p>Based on related studies:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Leaders should manage their teams and demonstrate commitment to the organization’s core values (Tenney, 2020).

B. Camaraderie Factor

Table 5 shows the suggestions of respondents, and the recommendations based on related studies. These initiatives are focused on partnership culture, specifically about openly interacting with colleagues from different teams.

Table 5. Suggestions and recommendations to enhance specific areas of ‘achievement’ factor to improve employee retention

Specific Area	Enhancement Suggestions
Can openly interact with colleagues from different teams	<p>From respondents:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Activities like online team building and other fun activities can be organized to better know peers at work. 2. More cross-functional knowledge and effective communication programs would be beneficial for internal productivity and customer experience. <p>Based on related studies:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Encourage open, transparent, and consistent communication (Sheetz, 2020). 2. Conduct programs to improve connection and collaboration (Vance, 2023).

C. Equity Factor

To further improve the retention rate of the organization, the engagement elements under equity which garnered negative employee reactions must be improved. The table 6 below exhibits the suggestions of the respondents, and the recommendations based on related studies.

Table 6. Suggestions and recommendations to enhance specific area of ‘equity’ factor to improve employee retention

Specific Area	Enhancement Suggestions
Has work-life balance	<p>From respondents:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Invest in Change Management resources to evaluate individual contributor workloads to balance with the company’s continuous growth. <p>Based on related studies:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Provide remote work options or a 4-day work week if possible. 2. Let employees take mental health days and time off when they need to rest and recharge (Paulsen, 2021).
Communicates openly and	<p>Based on related studies:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Share facts about the layoff.

honestly about layoffs	2. Give assistance to laid-off workers and provide support for the remaining employees (Edwards, 2024).
Provided with variable pay	<p>From respondents:</p> <p>1. Provide bonuses, commissions or merit pay to employees below the managerial level.</p> <p>Based on related studies:</p> <p>1. Provide team awards for resolving a significant work challenge, completing special projects or developing new ideas (Indeed Editorial Team, 2022).</p> <p>2. Use the 3P salary payment system designed to reflect three factors in each employee's income. Pay for Position is given to ensure fair compensation based on members' job function and market standards. Pay for People rewards workers for their individual expertise and contributions. Pay for Performance is provided to motivate employees to perform at their best and achieve business targets (Nguyen, 2023).</p> <p>3. Offer flexible benefits where employees can choose or customize perks according to their individual needs. Typically, benefits plan like this work with each employee having a monthly or annual allowance and the cost of their usage will be reimbursed by the company (Walker, 2023).</p>
Pays attention to the wants and needs of employees	<p>From respondents:</p> <p>1. Conduct annual feedback gathering from employees</p> <p>2. Schedule focus groups with managers and their teams to find out blockers and other issues</p> <p>Based on related studies:</p> <p>1. Conduct stay and exit interviews (Eagle Hill Consulting, 2022).</p> <p>2. Conduct pulse surveys, anonymous Q and As and regular town halls (Baker & Sutner, 2022).</p>

Summary of Findings

To summarize the key points based on the collected data in terms of levels of employee reactions on existing retention strategies for each engagement factor, achievement, camaraderie and equity, the following significant themes emerged:

1. The company already has existing employee retention strategies which revolves around the engagement factors mentioned in this research. In terms of 'achievement', they currently have a learning and development platform with different types of professional educational programs, job enrichment programs as well as tuition reimbursement. They also conduct recognition programs to reward loyalty, excellent performance, and adherence to core values. For 'camaraderie', they formed two groups to amplify interpersonal relationships within the organization. One was for social connections and the other was for diversity and

inclusion. They also championed volunteering and social services which significantly affected employee morale. And lastly, initiatives for 'equity' focused on wellness, remote work set-up, flexible working schedule, annual salary increases and bonuses for managerial employees and above. Though they had various programs under each engagement factor, respondents still felt the need for additional or enhanced strategies as reflected in the responses given during the survey.

2. The engagement factor 'camaraderie' gained the highest combined positive reaction result at 90% which means that employees felt enthusiastic and satisfied with the retention strategies for this factor. This was followed by 'achievement' which received an average percentage of 87% positive employee reactions while 'equity' garnered 86%. This implies that the retention strategies for these specific engagement elements should be revisited and improved.
3. Under each engagement factor, the elements which received most of the negative employee reactions must be the focus of strategy enhancement. For the 'achievement' factor, respondents answered that initiatives for training and learning opportunities (35%) must be improved. In terms of 'camaraderie' factor, open interaction with colleagues from different teams (12%) garnered the highest negative employee reactions. This implies that various activities must be organized to meet peers inside the workplace and there must be better communication between departments or teams as this is beneficial for both productivity and customer experience. In connection with 'equity', providing variable pay (38%) got most of the negative employee reactions. The employees who completed the survey indicated that performance bonuses or commissions should also be given to employees who were below managerial level. This approach will reinforce the sense of accomplishment for individual contributors or team members.

Conclusions

The research has established the following conclusions as supported by the results and data gathered:

1. The existing retention strategies of the organization covers the three engagement factors which are achievement, camaraderie, and equity. However, they still need to perform a review and enhancement of the existing strategies based on the results of this study. Also, respondents were very open, and they shared some suggestions which they think would be appropriate to further improve talent retention in the workplace.
2. Though all engagement factors and elements garnered more than 62% of combined positive reactions, some specific areas of 'achievement' and 'equity' need retention strategy enhancements as they gained 26% - 38% of combined negative reactions. This portion of responses indicates that employee engagement is low in the said areas, and they could contribute to attrition sooner or later.

3. For each engagement factor, the specific areas which gained most of the negative employee reactions need retention strategy enhancement. In terms of 'achievement', they want improvements on the initiatives for training and learning opportunities. For 'camaraderie', open interaction with colleagues from different teams must be strengthened. In connection with 'equity', providing variable pay should also be considered by the management to provide higher engagement levels for the company's workforce thus resulting to lower attrition and better employee retention rates.

Recommendations

In the light of the research findings, as a general recommendation for the company, they can consider shifting to a Data-Driven HR Model. They can use HR analytics as the tool to adapt in this data-driven method which involves collecting, analyzing, and reporting HR data to drive business results. It enables companies to better understand the workforce, make decisions based on data, and measure the impact of current strategies, ultimately improving overall business performance. Furthermore, it helps test the effectiveness of HR policies and interventions. Most importantly, analyzing HR data helps draw conclusions, uncover insights, and make predictions in various HR functions like recruitment, engagement, employee turnover, retirement projections and retention. Also, in terms of salary review, the company may benchmark with other firms in the same industry as well as make salary survey reports from a basis to make compensation and benefits packages competitive.

Additionally, this study identified opportunities for similar or related research. Future studies may focus on enhancing the current knowledge to serve as guide for creating organizational strategies. Researchers could explore the dynamics as well as the long-term effects of employee engagement and retention by conducting longitudinal studies. By monitoring employee engagement levels and retention rates over an extended period, researchers can discover trends, causal connections, and intervening factors that influence the results.

Globally, future research can also focus on investigating the correlation between engagement and retention including other themes such as diversity, and inclusion. Through this, it is possible to detect cultural factors that impact employee engagement and retention which can help in developing strategies for diverse cultural settings. And as technology keeps advancing, future studies can investigate how it affects retention and engagement as well. It is imperative to understand the ways in which technology can be utilized to augment engagement and retention in the workplace.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers certify that they have obtained the research participants' informed consent. Additionally, they guarantee that the information gathered from respondents remains anonymous. The study process was carried out strictly in accordance with

plagiarism regulations, guaranteeing that the findings were assessed objectively and that their application was restricted to this research only.

Acknowledgments

The researchers are sincerely thankful to our family and friends for their continuous support and encouragement during the entire research process.

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